

Influence of Job Rotations on the Development of Project Employee Skills: A Case of the HIV PMTCT Project, MTRH, Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Globally, projects and organizations value the positive contributions that employees make toward overall performance. On-the-job training methods have increasingly been recognized as effective strategies for enhancing and developing employee skills. However, many African countries continue to underutilize job rotation as a form of on-the-job training, despite its proven benefits. This study aimed to examine the influence of job rotations on the development of project employee skills within the HIV PMTCT Project at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital (MTRH), Kenya. The study was guided by the Supervisor's Career Development Theory and employed a descriptive survey research design using quantitative approaches. The target population comprised 184 employees of the HIV PMTCT Project, from which a sample of 126 respondents was selected using Yamane's (1970) sample size determination formula and stratified sampling technique. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed through descriptive statistics, including means, frequencies, and percentages. The study revealed a composite mean score of 4.02 (SD = 0.28), indicating that job rotations significantly enhance employee skills development in project settings. The findings further showed that the HIV PMTCT Project effectively applies job rotations as a practical on-the-job training method. The study concludes that job rotations play a critical role in enhancing employee skills development and should be integrated into human resource strategies for staff training. It recommends that project and organizational management adopt job rotations as a routine practice in employee training and development at all levels.

Keywords: Training, Job Rotation, Employee, Skills Development, Projects

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, projects and businesses value the positive contributions employees make to overall organizational performance (Nassazi, 2013). Many countries are increasingly developing career and employee development programs focused on improving workplace skills and productivity. Human resource development programs often include both on-the-job and off-the-job training approaches, which are instrumental in building employee capacity. Among these, on-the-job training methods have gained recognition for their direct impact on employee skill enhancement. According to Rodriguez and Walters (2017), on-the-job training refers to methods implemented within the workplace to improve and develop employee competencies. It is, therefore, imperative that organizations and projects, both locally and internationally, embrace on-the-job training to foster employee growth.

In Europe, the use of on-the-job training methods in enhancing employee skills is consistent and often preferred over off-the-job training. Similarly, in the United States, Knight and Parker (2021) observed that on-the-job training is a dominant approach within project environments. For example, Abey Inc. and the Solar Energy Project in the U.S. integrate job rotations into their operational procedures to expose employees to a wide range of skills across different departments. In Pakistan, Chongcharoen and Ulhaq (2019) noted that projects favor on-the-job training to improve employees' interpersonal and diagnostic abilities, a trend mirrored in China, where both on- and off-the-job methods are used to develop team competence. These studies collectively demonstrate that on-the-job training significantly contributes to employee skill development.

However, Ling and Wong (2016) found that many African countries prioritize training programs that offer financial incentives rather than long-term skill development. They argue that off-the-job training often attracts allowances and per diems, making it more appealing to employees than skill-based on-the-job approaches. At Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital (MTRH), management within the AMPATH Project has, in recent years, advocated for increased use of on-the-job training, particularly job rotations, to improve employee skills and productivity. This approach aims to enhance staff competence efficiently while reducing training costs in both the short and long term.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Effective training and development programs are essential for improving employee performance (Milner, McCarthy, & Milner, 2018). Research indicates that training systematically enhances employees' skills, knowledge, and competencies required for optimal job performance. Although numerous studies have demonstrated a positive relationship between general training and employee productivity, few have specifically examined the impact of on-the-job training methods such as job rotation. In Africa, the adoption of job rotation remains relatively low despite its potential to develop diverse skills among employees. Linge (2019) established that job rotation significantly contributes to skill development; however, the study focused broadly on training and productivity rather than the specific influence of job rotation. The adoption of on-the-job training methods by the AMPATH Project at MTRH presents a practical opportunity to empirically assess their impact on employee skill development. Despite extensive literature on training and performance, limited research has explored how job rotation specifically affects the development of project employees' skills, creating a critical research gap that this study sought to address.

1.3 Research Objective

To establish the influence of job rotations on the development of project employee skills in the HIV PMTCT Project, MTRH, Kenya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Employee Skills Development

Employee skills development is a critical component in achieving organizational goals and objectives. Rafiq (2015) defines employee skills development as the process of identifying skill gaps and enhancing employees' competencies to bridge those gaps. Similarly, Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016) describe it as a systematic process of identifying relevant skills and abilities necessary for the attainment of organizational objectives. According to Rafiq (2015), organizations bear the responsibility of determining the essential skills required by their employees and designing mechanisms to upgrade these skills in alignment with job requirements. Elnaga et al. (2013) further outline several benefits derived from employee skills development, including increased employee confidence, improved decision-making capacity, creation of new opportunities, stimulation of creativity, and a deeper understanding of industry operations. Collectively, these outcomes emphasize that a well-developed workforce is instrumental in enhancing organizational performance and competitiveness.

2.2 Job Rotation and Employee Skills Development

Organizations often employ job rotation as part of their on-the-job training (OJT) and human resource development strategies. Kampkötter, Harbring, and Sliwka (2018) define job rotation as a managerial technique involving the systematic shifting of employees across various work environments at regular intervals. Similarly, Akbari and Maniei (2017) describe job rotation as a planned process in which employees are transferred horizontally or vertically among jobs to acquire and refine diverse skills. The authors further observe that job rotation not only enhances employee satisfaction but also facilitates cross-training, allowing employees to gain a broad range of knowledge and competencies essential for achieving organizational objectives.

Several studies affirm the usefulness of job rotation in promoting employee skills development. Mohan and Gomathi (2015), in a descriptive study, found that job rotation significantly empowered nurses to understand different dimensions of hospital work systems and improve their performance in patient care. Their results showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.79$) between job rotation and employee performance. Similarly, Akbari and Maniei (2017), in a survey of Dana Insurance employees, found a significant relationship between job rotation and employee performance, confirming the positive effect of job rotation practices on skill enhancement.

Contrary findings, however, have also been reported. Jocom, Lambey, and Pandowo (2017), studying employees of Pegadaian (Persero) Manado, observed that job rotation had no significant impact on employees' job knowledge. They noted that employees preferred job stability over frequent movement across roles. Likewise, Kampkötter, Harbring, and Sliwka (2018) found no significant relationship between job rotation and future employee performance in the financial services industry. Their study suggested that organizations should focus job rotation programs primarily on high performers, as low-performing employees may not experience performance gains through rotation.

In South Africa, Dayanath and Sanjana (2014) investigated the impact of job rotation on job security and productivity among employees in a textile company located in KwaZulu-Natal.

Their findings revealed that job rotation had a substantial positive influence on both job security and productivity. The study further indicated that job rotation encouraged the acquisition of new skills, enhanced motivation, and reduced employee turnover by exposing workers to new work environments and challenges. The authors recommended that organizations strengthen and sustain job rotation programs to promote productivity and employee development.

Further empirical evidence supports the relationship between job rotation and indicators of skills development. Linge (2019), in a descriptive survey of ICT firms in Nairobi, established a significant association between job rotation and employees' technical ability to perform their tasks ($\chi^2 = 0.135$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, Tuei and Saina (2015), in a case study of Kenya Commercial Bank (KCB) branches in the North Rift Region, reported that job rotation contributed to 55.29% of employee motivation at the workplace. The findings suggest that job rotation fosters motivation and engagement, thereby improving employee performance and commitment.

A documentary review by Hochdörffer, Hedler, and Lanza (2018) examined the determinants of effective job rotation and scheduling programs in manufacturing firms. The study identified standardized procedures, demographic characteristics, scheduling periods, and structured rotation plans as key components of effective job rotation systems. When these factors are properly integrated, they are found to positively influence employees' technical competencies. The authors recommended the adoption of short-term planning systems that holistically incorporate these factors to enhance the success of job rotation and staff scheduling programs.

Other scholars have explored the psychological and demographic aspects influencing the suitability of job rotation. Boenzi, Digiesi, Mossa, Mummolo, and Romano (2015) investigated the psychological effects of job rotation among older employees. The study revealed that the nature and appropriateness of the work strongly determine the acceptability of job rotation among aged workers. Older employees were less likely to embrace job rotation due to resistance to acquiring new skills, indicating a negative relationship between age and skills acquisition through rotation. The authors concluded that managers should consider employees' age and psychological readiness when designing job rotation programs to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness. The development of employee skills (technical, interpersonal, and cognitive skills) depends on the job rotations (vertical, lateral, and job movements) conducted in the organization.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Job Rotations

Development of Project Employee Skills

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2.4 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Supervisory Career Development Theory, originally proposed by Frank Parsons (1909), which emphasizes aligning individuals with job roles that best fit their characteristics. The theory posits that individuals can be effectively matched to vocational opportunities based on their abilities, skills, and interests. Parsons argued that when these personal attributes are appropriately stimulated, they influence career decisions, leading individuals to choose professions that align with their interests, abilities, and personalities. Once a career decision is made, individuals tend to remain within that vocational path, as their choices are shaped by intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. Furthermore, Super (1909) expanded on Parsons' ideas, suggesting that career choices are determined not only by personal attributes but also by economic, social, environmental, and physical factors. These external conditions interact with individual traits to influence one's ability and willingness to pursue specific work roles. The relevance of this theory to the present study lies in its recognition that training and development can enhance an individual's ability and interest to perform effectively within a job. In organizational contexts, factors such as workplace culture, available resources, and environmental conditions can significantly shape employee engagement and adaptability in new job settings. However, a noted limitation of this theory is its narrow focus on abilities and interests, while overlooking the critical role of knowledge acquisition and skill enhancement—key components of employee development. In the modern workplace, continuous learning and skills upgrading are equally vital for effective performance and long-term career growth.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design that incorporated quantitative research approaches. According to Kothari (2003), a descriptive survey design involves a comprehensive examination of study variables to obtain accurate and detailed information about the phenomenon under investigation. The target population comprised 184 employees working under the HIV PMTCT Project, including the project manager, project accountants, secretaries, drivers, caregivers, nurses, doctors, and other subordinate staff. The actual number of project staff was verified using official records from the MTRH AMPATH Human Resource Office (2022). To determine the sample size, the study applied Yamane's (1970) formula for sample size determination at a 95% confidence level, as presented below.

$$n = \frac{N}{N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

e = sampling error (5%)

N= Population size

$$n = \frac{184}{1+184(0.05)^2}$$

Sample size 126

The sample size, determined at a 95% significance level, comprised 126 respondents. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure fair representation across different staff categories. Each of the 184 project employees was assigned a number, after which random numbers were drawn from a bin, and 126 participants were selected to represent the target population. Data were collected using questionnaires, which served as the primary research

instrument. According to Saharan and Boogie (2010), a questionnaire is a structured set of questions designed according to the themes of a study to elicit specific information from a target group. The collected data were filtered, organized, labeled, and coded before analysis. The study utilized the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 as the main analytical tool. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, specifically measures of central tendency such as means, frequencies, and percentages, to summarize and interpret the findings effectively.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Job Rotations and Project Employee Skills Development

The objective of this study was to examine the influence of job rotation on employee skills development. To achieve this, descriptive statistics were employed to analyze and describe the relationship between job rotation practices and the development of employee skills. A total of 126 respondents constituted the study sample. All respondents were issued questionnaires, and all 126 were completed and returned, representing a 100% response rate, which indicates a high level of participant engagement and data reliability. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics illustrating the relationship between job rotation and employee skills development.

Table 1: Job Rotations and Employee Skills Development

Statements	1(F, %)	2(F, %)	3(F, %)	4(F, %)	5(F, %)	Mean	SD
The number of employee vertical job movements has improved the level of cognitive skills.	9(7.1)	11(8.7)	2(1.6)	59(46.8)	45(35.7)	3.90	0.11
The frequency of lateral job movements has helped to develop the level of technical skills	5(4.0)	14(11.1)	4(3.2)	48(38.1)	55(43.7)	4.06	0.34
The number of job movements has improved employee interpersonal skills.	3(2.4)	8(6.3)	1(1.0)	56(44.4)	58(46.0)	4.25	0.21
The nature of task rotations has enabled the improvement of the level of technical skills.	12(10)	14(11.1)	2(1.6)	54(42.9)	44(34.9)	3.83	0.44
Composite mean & SD						4.02	0.28

Table 1 shows that respondents, with a mean score of 3.90 (SD = 0.11), indicated that employee vertical job movements have, to a moderate extent, improved the level of cognitive skills among employees. Specifically, 46.8% and 35.7% of respondents stated that vertical job movements enhanced cognitive skills to a moderate and great extent, respectively. Only 7.1% and 8.7% of respondents reported that such movements never or rarely improved cognitive skills, while 1.6% did not respond. These findings align with Akbari and Maniei (2017), who observed that vertical job rotations expose employees to new and challenging tasks, thereby enhancing diagnostic and cognitive abilities. A mean score of 4.06 (SD = 0.34) further revealed that, to a moderate extent, the frequency of lateral job movements has contributed to the

development of technical skills among employees. Supporting this, 43.7% and 38.1% of respondents indicated that lateral job movements had improved technical skills to a great and moderate extent, respectively, while 4.0% and 11.1% reported that such movements had never or rarely influenced skill development. Linge (2019) supports this observation, noting that lateral movements enhance employee motivation and facilitate the acquisition of new technical competencies in different work environments.

In addition, the study found that respondents, with a mean score of 4.25 (SD = 0.21), agreed to a great extent that job movements have improved interpersonal skills among employees. Specifically, 46% and 44.4% reported that job movements enhanced interpersonal skills to a moderate and great extent, respectively, whereas 6.3% and 2.4% indicated that such improvement never or rarely occurred. These results are supported by Jocom, Lambey, and Pandowo (2017), who emphasized that job movements enhance interaction and collaboration across departments, thereby strengthening interpersonal relationships within organizations. Furthermore, respondents, with a mean score of 3.83 (SD = 0.44), indicated that the nature of task rotations has, to a great extent, improved the level of technical skills among employees. Supporting data showed that 42.9% and 34.9% of respondents acknowledged that task rotations enhanced technical skills to a moderate and great extent, respectively, while 10% and 11% reported never or rarely experiencing such improvement. Antony (2018) supports this finding, asserting that task rotations are instrumental in fostering employee skill development.

Overall, a composite mean of 4.02 (SD = 0.28) indicates that job rotations, to a moderate extent, significantly enhance employee skills development within project environments. These results are consistent with the findings of Akbari and Maniei (2017) and Hochdorffer, Hedler, and Lanza (2018), who concluded that job rotations have a positive predictive effect on employee skill advancement. Consequently, it is recommended that human resource personnel and project managers incorporate job rotation as an integral component of training and development strategies to enhance employee competencies and overall project performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that job rotations influence the implementation of project employee skills development. Job rotations were found to have a moderate influence on the implementation of employee skills development. Vertical job movements, lateral job movements, the number of job movements, and task rotations make a great deal of contribution to cognitive and interpersonal skills, respectively. The management and employees need to embrace the various forms of job rotations because they are associated with the development of technical skills in the organization. The study therefore recommends that management of the organizations and projects needs to embrace job rotations as part of their training programs in the organization.

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